

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D4.1 Description of demonstration use cases

31/08/2024

Lead Beneficiary: UGOT, LifeWatch

Authors: Matthias Obst (UGOT), Cristina Huertas (LifeWatch)

Project Title	Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean
Project Acronym	DTO-BioFlow
Project Number	101112823
Type of project	IA – Innovation Action
Topics	HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01-07
Starting date of Project	01 September 2023
Duration of the project	42 months
Website	https://dto-bioflow.eu/

D4.1 – Description of demonstration use cases

Work Package	WP4 Demonstrate with policy-relevant use cases the benefit of an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring
Task	T4.1 Development and implementation of the demonstration use cases (DUCs) to deliver an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring through the digital environment
Lead author	Matthias Obst (UGOT), Cristina Huertas (LifeWatch ERIC)
Contributors	Christina Pavludi (EMBRC-ERIC), Alice Soccodato (EMBRC-ERIC), Christos Arvanitidis (LifeWatch ERIC), Lotte Pohl (VLIZ), Asbjorn Christensen (DTU), Jan Reubens (VLIZ), Patrizio Mariani (DTU), Kim Aarestrup (DTU), Carlota Muñiz (VLIZ), Elisabeth Debusschere (VLIZ), Jo-Hannes Nowé (VLIZ), Peter Tyack (USTAN), Jakob Tougaard (AU), Emily T Griffiths (AU), Rune Lagaisse (VLIZ), Felipe Artigas (CNRS ULC O), Ankita Vaswani (Hereon), Klas Ove Moeller (HEREON), Gert Everaert (VLIZ), Pascal Hablützel (VLIZ), Isabel Sousa Pinto (CIIMAR), Irene Martins (CIIMAR), Carlota Gouveia (CIIMAR), Gabriela Oliveira (CIIMAR), Heidi Tillin (PML), Dan Lear (MBA), Harvey Tyler-Walters (MBA), Ute Brönnner (SOCEAN), Muriel Dunn (SOCEAN), Ralph Stevenson-Jones (SOCEAN), Raymond Nepstad (SOCEAN), Neil Holdsworth (ICES), Arne Berre (SINDIG), Madeleine Walker (SU), Lionel Guidi (CNRS), Hervé Claustre (CNRS), Jean-Olivier Irisson (SU), Gabriela Martinez Balbontin (MOi), Stefano Ciavatta (MOi)
Peer reviewers	Vicente Fernandez (SSBE), Christos Arvanitidis (LifeWatch ERIC), Carlota Muñiz (VLIZ)
Version	V1.0
Due Date	31/08/2024
Submission Date	31/08/2024

Dissemination Level

X	PU: Public
	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)
	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	25/07/2024	Matthias Obst (UGOT), Cristina Huertas (LifeWatch)	First draft
0.2	15/08/2024	WP leaders	Review by WP leaders
0.3	26/08/2024	Vicente Fernandez (SSBE), Christos Arvanitidis (LifeWatch)	Internal peer review
0.4	28/08/2024	Carlota Muñiz (VLIZ)	Internal peer review
1.0	30/08/2024	Submission	

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
AI	Artificial intelligence
BGC-Argo	Biogeochemical Argo
BRUV	Baited Remote Underwater Video
BWMC	Ballast water management convention
DT	Digital twin
DTO	Digital twin of the ocean
DUC	Demonstration Use Cases
DUC components	Functions connecting biodiversity data to digital applications
DUC features	General characteristics of digital twins
EOO	Extend of occurrence
ES	Ecosystem Service
HELCOM	Helsinki Commission
IoT	Internet of things
LTA	Low trophic aquacultures
ML	Machine learning
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NIS	Non-indigenous species
OSPAR	Oslo and Paris Conventions
OWF	Offshore wind farms
PHI	Pelagic Habitat Indicators
PSD	Particle size distribution
SDM	Species distribution model
SwAM	Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management
UVP	Underwater Vision Profiler
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

WP	Work Package
----	--------------

Keywords

Digital twin, ocean, biodiversity monitoring, data integration, data gaps, demonstrator, use cases, DTO, data sources, ecosystem management, monitoring networks.

Disclaimer

The DTO-BioFlow project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101112823. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report outlines the design of the demonstrator use cases (DUCs) which are the scientific investigations that guide the implementation of biological data and analysis resources into the Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO). In the first 10 months of the DTO-BioFlow project WP4 has designed eight DUCs, covering a wide range of ecosystem management topics, by including invasive species management, adaptive offshore construction, pelagic biodiversity assessments, marine aquaculture, management of marine protected areas, and marine carbon sequestration. The ambition of the DUCs is to deliver end-to-end approaches that connect biodiversity monitoring to ecosystem management through the digital environment. This report contains two main chapters. Chapter 1 provides some important conceptual introductions, which are necessary to agree on what DUCs can deliver and how to monitor progress with the implementation of the DUCs. We propose a series of essential features that should be demonstrated by the DUCs as well as key criteria that need to be fulfilled even if DUCs change or if new DUCs are added in the future. In chapter 2 we provide detailed descriptions of the scientific investigations planned in each DUC. Here we emphasise the relations to data sources and underlying monitoring networks as well as analytical services needed. These are the initial specifications to WP2, 3 and 5, which should help prioritising implementation of data and tools. We also add explanations of expected outcomes, stakeholder involvement, and add a short risk assessment to each DUC.

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. Introduction	7
1.1. The purpose of this document.....	7
1.2. Digital Twin concept	8
1.3. Essential components and key criteria for DUCs	10
1.4. Expectation management continuous evaluation of DUCs	12
2. Description of Demonstration use cases (DUCs)	12
2.1 DUC 1 on invasive species management	13
2.2. DUC 2 on the Impact from offshore infrastructures.....	16
2.3 DUC 3 on assessing pelagic biodiversity and human impact	19
2.4 DUC 4 for spatial planning of sustainable mariculture	21
2.5. DUC 5 Ecosystem-based spatial planning and MPA management	24
2.6 DUC 6 on lower-trophic level biomass monitoring to inform ocean governance	28
2.7 DUC 7 on ecosystem services, including carbon sequestration.....	31
2.8 DUC 8 on Machine Learning for ocean colour seasonal forecasting (chlorophyll-a and primary production).....	34
3. Conclusions	36
4. References	37

1. Introduction

1.1. The purpose of this document

The European Commission is committed to build a European Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), a virtual representation of marine and coastal environments (www.edito.eu). This goal is well-aligned with [the United Nations Ocean Science program for Sustainable Development](#) which likewise aims to create a digital representation of the ocean by 2030 (Calewaert et al. 2024). The central ambition of the EU DTO is to enable policymakers, researchers, industry, and the public to become partners in the development of ocean management strategies and together safeguard a healthy and productive ocean. This implies access to marine data and creation of collective knowledge about impacts of climate change and human activities in the ocean.

The DTO-BioFlow project will generate specific contributions to this goal by developing DTO infrastructure resources as well as research outputs such as data products, applications, know how, and expert networks that will be used in marine research, protection and management of marine ecosystems. In the DTO-BioFlow project, Work package 4 (WP4) has the aim to design and implement a series of demonstration use cases (DUCs), which will guide the implementation of biological data and analytical resources into the EU DTO over the coming years. The ambition of the DUCs is to deliver end-to-end approaches connecting biodiversity monitoring to ecosystem management through the digital environment.

Given the high-level ambitions of the EU DTO and the fact that DTO-BioFlow is among the first projects to implement biological data and analysis resources, it is important that the DUCs capture essential characteristics of a digital twin and not merely demonstrate complex analytics. This will be spelled out in detail in the next section. DUCs also need to be part of scientific narratives that support the high-level strategic goals of the European Commission and the UN Ocean Decade program as well as similar ambitions to reconstruct marine ecosystems on a grand scale (The European Green Deal 2019; Nativi et al. 2021; Hassani et al. 2022). To this end, WP4 needs to define the essential features that should be demonstrated by the DUCs and suggest criteria that should be fulfilled by all DUCs. This conceptual outline will then be followed by descriptions of the scientific investigations planned for each DUC with emphasis on specific data resources, analytical capacities, expected outcomes, and stakeholder involvement.

It is important that the DUCs are realistically designed regarding available resources and time, that their development is practically feasible, and that existing resources are used or mobilised as much as possible. DUCs are also building up on new types of biodiversity data (i.e. genomic data, plankton imaging, biologging and passive acoustics) which is a novelty on itself, and they pose their own challenges for tool development. In other words, the challenge for each DUC is to showcase scientific and technical novelties while producing outcomes that are practically applicable. The DUCs that succeed with this task will not only be able to offer novel analytical applications, but also provide guiding examples for how user-driven and agile development of DTO resources can be organised across different research communities and technology sectors. Thereby, the DUCs can provide blueprints that demonstrate how the EU DTO can successively be built “*together with*” rather than “*for*” its user community.

Another contribution of the DUCs to the EU DTO development will be the documentation of missing data, models, and algorithms, as well as service gaps necessary to complete an end-to-end connection between ecological monitoring and digital applications in marine ecosystem management. Although the DTO would incorporate any lacking information in precautionary planning, the DUCs will be instrumental in identifying missing knowledge and experts from the field of science and technology who should continue working together beyond the lifetime of this project to construct the EU DTO.

The purpose of this document is to propose an initial set of scientific use cases, as a base for further discussion and continuous elaboration by the consortium and for helping all other work packages to prioritize the implementation of biological data and analytical resources into the EU DTO.

1.2. Digital Twin concept

A digital twin (DT) is defined as a virtual model that replicates the physical properties of a system (Rasheed et al. 2020). These virtual models are used to digitally explore performance, identify inefficiencies, and design solutions to improve their physical counterparts. In other words, DTs provide better insight into system dynamics by combining *a priori* knowledge on the mechanics and dynamics of a system through mathematical models with online data acquired from sensors and instruments deployed in the system for the monitoring of its primary variables. In contrast to simulations, which typically operate in entirely virtual dimensions, DTs are synchronised with sensors (e.g., satellites, temperature loggers, underwater cameras) that continuously update their virtual counterparts in real time with high-quality data (Fig. 1). DTs also make use of new technology such as Internet of things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and cloud computing (Rasheed et al. 2020). Based on the digital results, the physical twin can change and adapt through continuous alignment with its virtual counterpart, a valuable characteristic of all digital twins (Jones et al. 2020) and vice versa. According to an initial concept by Grieves (2014) a DT is defined as consisting of three components, (a) a physical product, (b) a virtual representation of that product, also called the digital twin model, and (c) the bi-directional connections that feed data from the physical to the virtual representation, while transferring information and processes from the virtual to the physical representation (Fig. 1). Once, these connections are established, DTs not only provide better understanding of system dynamics, but they also offer real-time or short time reactivity that help identifying and modulate system anomalies (de Koning et al. 2023).

Figure 1. Illustration of essential characteristics of a Digital twin (DT). The “Twinning” reconciles and matches the physical system (a) and the virtual system (b) with the help of the bi-directional flow of information (c). Figure modified from Jones et al. (2020). Grieves (2014) depicted these characteristics in a (mirroring or twinning) cycle where data are transferred from the physical to the virtual system, and information or processes are transferred from the virtual to the physical system.

The concept of DTs originated from engineering and life-cycle management (Grieves & Vickers 2016; Fuller et al. 2020) and is typically used to understand and optimise the performance of human-built systems (e.g., airplanes, production lines). However, DTs are today also developed to mimic and understand behaviour of “natural systems” such as weather (Rasheed et al. 2020) and the human body (Björnsson et al. 2019; Laubenbacher et al. 2021; Li et al. 2022). More recently, the concept has become established in ecology with DTs designed for terrestrial and marine ecosystems (de Koning et al. 2024). As the general DT concept starts to revitalise systems ecology (Evans et al. 2013; Dietze et al. 2018),

it is important to distinguish between general principles of DTs that apply across all scientific and engineering domains from those that are discipline-specific and in our case only apply to the purpose of marine ecology, conservation, and ecosystem management. It is also crucial to manage expectations of stakeholders and scientists regarding what the DTO can do and cannot do at this stage (de Koning et al. 2024). For this purpose, the DUCs will be instrumental; hence, we will outline below important conceptual features of a DT that should be represented by the DUCs. We summarise these general DT features in Table 1 and suggest revisiting these features continuously throughout the lifetime of the project to assess the progress of the DUCs regarding how well they align with the DT concept.

As we transfer the concept of the DT into the marine realm and more specifically apply it to marine ecology and ecosystem management, it is important to agree on the core purpose of the applications to be developed. Typical optimisation criteria for industrial DTs are efficiency, economy, scalability, and durability (Perez et al. 2022). However, these may not apply to the DUCs developed in DTO-BioFlow. It has been shown that DTs can be developed for marine systems (e.g., in aquaculture and fishing) with the sole purpose to optimise production or harvest of animal food, or in some examples to optimise animal welfare (Före et al. 2024; Budaev et al. 2024). In these cases, ecological sustainability and biodiversity positivity may not be relevant optimisation criteria for the performance assessments of these DTs. As an example, oxygen conditions can be measured to eventually predict fish growth in a DT entirely for the purpose to maximise the yield. Hence, each DUC should be clear about its optimisation objectives and associated criteria, including which system properties should be assessed. We propose here that all DUCs should measure system parameters that **help to better predict the state of marine biodiversity and improve ecological sustainability**.

According to Jones et al. (2020) one of the main purposes of DTs is to improve the performance of the physical entities interacting in a system. Such improvement or **system optimisation** is typically achieved through re-engineering of relevant components in the system and subsequent performance assessments. This concept is directly applicable to the optimisation of marine ecosystems through the re-arrangement of its physical, biological, and human components. In this project, we include one DUC exploring this DT feature by digitally engineering ecosystems for achieving marine sustainability targets (Table 1).

DTs may not only be used for system optimisation alone but also can be helpful to **sense and anticipate significant events or anomalies** and thereby enable fast and effective responses in system management. Examples in marine ecology include early-warning applications for alien species invasion events (Kraus 2023), predictions of harmful algal blooms (Stumpf et al. 2009), or anticipation of marine heat wave impacts (Hartog et al. 2023). At this stage four of the DUCs have an early-warning and/or predictive capability component (Table 1).

Another purpose of DTs in academic research is to **accelerate scientific outputs** through boosting either quality or efficiency of research, while supporting interdisciplinarity through more comprehensive and integrated data analysis. In other words, DTs should aspire to produce scientific knowledge better, cheaper, or faster compared to conventional analytical approaches and open access to standardized and quality-controlled data sets of larger scale than typical today. WP4 will try to achieve this goal, although it may be difficult to specify in advance how the DUCs may outperform current analytical approaches in terms of efficiency. WP4 will however stimulate and document such added value as it becomes evident from the DUCs. At this stage three of the DUCs have the ambition to showcase the added value of the DTO through accelerating scientific outputs (Table 1).

As mentioned in the above chapter, an important part of a DT is the ability to **identify gaps in data coverage and analytical capabilities** (de Koning et al. 2024; Tessarolo et al. 2021). Especially in this early phase of DTO development, this is a tangible outcome of DUCs and will be useful to drive the development of DTO functionality forward. This is especially relevant in the context of scale in ecosystem research. Some DUCs will be designed for small spatial or temporal investigations (e.g., a local aquaculture facility), while others may have a continental focus and aim to analyse long-term ecological processes. For the second, it will not be possible to collect all necessary data and run extensive modelling experiments in the framework of DTO-BioFlow, but these DUCs nevertheless specify data needs as well as standards to be applied by emerging monitoring programs. The majority of the DUCs designed here (6 out of 8) will demonstrate this feature (Table 1).

DTs should likewise be used in **systems research and education** (e.g., for teaching ecological complexity and systems ecology). Being able to inspire the future generation of ecologists, encourage learning in such a vital yet complex subject matter, and ensure the passing on of essential knowledge about marine ecology is critical. This feature should likewise be represented by at least some DUCs and we have included two DUCs with this goal (Table 1). Its potential should be followed up and explored further throughout the implementation phase.

Finally, a critical part of the DT design is the direct involvement of product users. Hence, DUCs should be directly connected to relevant stakeholders, including scientific end users and policymakers in marine conservation and resource management (e.g., coastal development and tourism authorities). Alternatively, they may directly support marine and maritime industries (e.g., in shipping, fisheries, aquacultures, offshore wind parks, environmental consultancies) in their attempt to implement sustainability practices. In Chapter 2 we specify for each DUC how the relations to specific end user groups are established or further consolidated during the implementation phase.

Table 1. Overview of important DT features addressed by the DUCs. Although DUCs may have the potential to address several DT features, we indicate only two of the most important ones for each DUC.

DT features and added value provided by the DUCs	DUC							
	1 Invasive species	2 Offshore construction	3 Pelagic biodiversity	4 Sustainable mariculture	5 MPA management	6 Lower tropic monitoring	7 Carbon sequestration	8 NPP forecasting
System optimisation & engineering		X						
Sense and anticipate significant events	X					X		X
Accelerate scientific outputs			X				X	X
Identify data gaps & missing analytical capabilities	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Systems research and education				X	X			

1.3. Essential components and key criteria for DUCs

As defined in conceptual studies (Jones et al. 2020; Calewaert et al. 2024) the main components of a DT need to establish an interaction between physical and virtual systems. In the case of DTO-BioFlow this applies to marine ecosystems, including DT components for (i) observation and data collection, (ii) information systems for data management and publication, and (iii) virtual laboratories for analytics (Fig. 2). The DUCs will make use these components to run (iv) virtual experiments and thereafter (v) reflect on the outcome in some form of decision support action. The latter will not only identify missing data but will support decisions with clear information about confidence limits and what data would most efficiently reduce uncertainty and improve decision making. These actions, in turn, may lead to an intervention that modifies the physical system (e.g., by system engineering or improvement of observation methods and data

collection). Most of the work in the WP4 is concerned with the virtual experiments, but the DUC design needs to ensure a connection in the value chain from ocean observation to the digital application by stakeholders (Fig. 2). DUCs should be evaluated based on how well they connect these functional components, although they may not fully achieve such a connection throughout the project’s lifetime. The important contributions of the DUCs lie in the progress towards a full connection of all components. For example, a DUC may show that genetic sensor networks can be used to identify and predict sensitive habitats through detecting the presence of species that are sensitive to specific stressors. Such results will stimulate the establishment of genetic sensor networks for broad-scale monitoring of sensitive habitats in the future. The specific contribution of the DUC in this case may be the documentation of the necessary data products, associated data standards, and analytical assets to predict sensitive habitats.

Figure 2. Diagram illustrating how essential components of Demonstration Use Cases (DUCs) are linked in the value chain of biodiversity data. The goal for each DUC is to achieve an end-to-end connection of all components from “Observation & data collection” to “Feedback”. If possible, stakeholder involvement should lead to modulation of the Observation component. Real-world components are depicted in blue, while virtual components are depicted in green. Diagram modified from Calewaert et al. 2024.

An important objective of this document is to manage DUCs’ expectations and avoid misguided developments leading to DUCs that are not representative, too complex to be useful, or that remain purely academic without practical relevance to society. In this context it may help to formulate a set of key criteria to be fulfilled by all DUCs to be good examples of DTO applications. We suggest the following criteria for all DUCs.

Added value. All DUCs should include at least one of the DT features explained in chapter 1.2 and summarised in Table 1 and thereby showcase the added value of the DTO.

DTO components. Koning et al. (2023) states that “DTs are not just big models of everything, containing big data and machine learning. Rather, the strength of DTs is in combining data, models, and domain knowledge, and their continuous alignment with the real world”. Hence, all DUCs should reflect these general properties and link the essential components (i) - (v) as mentioned in chapter 1.3 and outlined in Figure 2. This includes an element of alignment between the virtual and physical space (i.e., the “Feedback” in Fig. 2). DUCs should be realistic and explicit about data products and analytical resources that can be provided by WP2, WP3 and WP5.

Co-creation. The resources in this project are limited, but the community of DTO developers and end users is growing fast. We expect that throughout the project lifetime new initiatives will arise eager to contribute to the DUCs. For the

sake of long-term sustainability and consolidation of DTO assets it is important to engage a wide range of stakeholders, including engineers, research infrastructures, and scientists. Accordingly, all DUCs should include an element of co-creation.

1.4. Expectation management continuous evaluation of DUCs

DTs have become a popular concept in ecology and marine science and stimulated lively discussions in the scientific community. Hence, it is important for this project not to overload DUCs with ambitions and make sure expectations remain realistic. We suggest that DUCs should attempt to implement few, or at least one of the above-mentioned conceptual features (Table 1) to demonstrate the added value of a Digital Twin. In addition, the DUCs are designed to inspire end users and scientific collaborators as well as guide the technical implementation of the EU DTO.

The original design of the DUCs may change throughout the project lifetime based on the results obtained from the implemented data and tools. This is expected, and for that reason all DUCs are accompanied by a short risk assessment. New DUCs may be added by external contributors in the coming years, if the Steering committee (StC) approves their applicability and implementation. We suggest here that any new or external DUC must match the criteria specified in chapter 1.3 to enter the implementation pipeline in DTO-BioFlow.

The current document marks the transition from the design into implementation phase (Fig. 3), which will gradually be replaced by the consolidation activities towards the end of the project.

Figure 3. Timeline for design, implementation, and consolidation of DUCs.

2. Description of Demonstration use cases (DUCs)

This chapter presents the DUCs as they have been designed in the first 10 months of the project. These are conceptual sketches presenting scientific study cases that contain important features and criteria mentioned in the previous chapters. Some of the DUCs focus on short temporal scale and act in small ecosystems, while others address broad-scale ecosystem dynamics. This is intentional as we would like to offer a breadth of potential DTO applications, while being able to stimulate various DTO components equally; some DUCs are more mature than others and therefore will drive forward the improvement of monitoring, data collection and management, while others will improve the development of analytical resources. DUCs may change, expand, or branch regarding their scientific scope, but should maintain a clear link to the above established principles. Finally, the scientific narrative of the DUCs will become more detailed as the technical implementation of data, tools, and services makes progress with the ambition to publish scientific results in peer-reviewed journals.

2.1. DUC 1 on invasive species management

Figure 4. Overview of physical (blue) and virtual (green) twin components linked in DUC 1.

DUC leader(s)* and participants with organization	Matthias Obst* (Department of Marine Sciences, University of Gothenburg), Cristina Huertas* (LifeWatch ERIC), Alice Soccodato (EMBRC-ERIC), Christina Pavloudi (EMBRC-ERIC), Christos Arvanitidis (LifeWatch ERIC)
Challenge and suggested solution	<p>Current approaches to detect, control and manage marine non-indigenous species (NIS) are based on limited data and analytical background. Hence, there is large uncertainty in environmental agencies about whether there should be a reaction to a new intrusion, how such a management activity should be designed, and if certain species, habitats or incidents should be prioritized over others. Nevertheless, through the legislation of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), all European countries are obliged to monitor and control NIS. MSFD also states that NIS-management efforts should be organized on regional or subregional level. Hence, a consistent approach to analyse and predict NIS would be beneficial for national and regional actors in Europe dealing with marine NIS management.</p> <p>This DUC combines NIS observations from genetic monitoring networks (EMO BON), citizen science alerts, and conventional systematic monitoring programs with marine environmental (e.g., temperature, salinity, etc.) and socio-economic (e.g., traffic, ports, marinas) data. This information will be analyzed to obtain early warning signals, and further to produce species distribution models (SDMs) that predict invasive hotspots and range shifts. In addition, genetic information will be used to explore continental-scale phylogeographic patterns and thereby detect migration routes and vectors along the Europe coastline. The results of these analyses are expected to help prioritize NIS management efforts and make NIS response faster.</p>
Biological monitoring and sensor resources	<p>Genetic monitoring networks (EMO BON)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Genetic monitoring observations

	<p>Citizen science networks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iNaturalist and national citizen science networks <p>Systematic and opportunistic observation networks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National biological monitoring networks for non-indigenous species
Data resources	<p>Genetic data from ENA (raw genetic data) from EMBRC-ERIC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amplicon-based metabarcoding sequence data from EMO BON (Water samples, Hard substrate) from European coastal observatories and from eDNA and plankton surveys available at https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB51688 and https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB72316 <p>Conventional observation data from GBIF and OBIS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic and opportunistic (incl. citizen science) monitoring data for alien species <p>Global environmental data layers (Bio-Oracle) from LifeWatch ERIC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine environmental data layers for past, current and future conditions <p>Socio-economic data from HELCOM/OSPAR</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine traffic, locations, and turnover in European ports and marinas
Analytical resources	<p>Bioinformatics pipelines from LifeWatch</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PEMA Pipeline for Environmental DNA Metabarcoding Analysis of the 16S/18S rRNA, ITS and COI marker genes, available at https://github.com/hariszaf/pema Implemented in the LifeWatch ERIC Tesseract VRE https://tesseract.lifewatch.dev/arms/dashboard <p>Biogeographical NIS detection workflows from LifeWatch</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WRIMS invasive species checker available at https://www.github.com/vliz-be-opsci/lw-iji-invasive-checker • Alien detective, nearest occurrence calculator for alien species, available at https://github.com/IrisVP/AlienDetective • Extend of occurrence (EOO) R-scripts <p>Species distribution modelling workflows from EMBRC-ERIC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MBO-D5.1 and MBO-D5.4 <p>Phylogeography tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software for haplotype networks and F_{st} statistics (based on R packages) • R packages: phyloseq (McMurdie & Holmes 2013), rgbif (Chamberlain et al. 2024), rnatuarearth (Massicotte & South 2024)
Expected outputs and feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyses will produce biogeographic maps showing expected and observed range shifts as well as early warning signals. Species distribution models will produce maps of potential NIS hotspots. Phylogeography will produce haplotype networks, maps of connectivity, and gene flow. Results are expected to contribute to inform measures to transition from sporadic to nationally coordinated genetic NIS monitoring, using network approach (i.e., repeated and standardised spatio-temporal sampling) • Target removal of detected NIS (e.g., <i>Styela clava</i>) • Apply for exemptions for ballast water treatment evaluated
DT features demonstrated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense and anticipate and react to significant events through early response to alien intrusions • Identify gaps in data coverage and analytical capabilities leading to improved monitoring programs
Stakeholders	<p>Target end users include individuals responsible for reporting and managing NIS in environmental agencies, municipalities, county boards, port administrations, and research institutes. Important regulations include MSFD and the Ballast water management convention (BWMC). More specifically, the DUC is based on active collaboration with the</p>

	Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management (SwAM), the Swedish Transport Agency, and the County Administrative Board of Western Sweden (Västra Götaland).
Status	Ready for implementation.

Risk assessment

Risk	Likelihood (1 low, 5 high)	Severity (1 low, 5 high)	Mitigation strategy
Genetic data not sufficient to improve range maps and SDMs.	3	2	We can still run SDM, including DNA-based observations and use genetic data for other analytics, e.g., meta phylogeography.
Environmental data not sufficient to improve SDMs.	3	2	We can still run SDM, but with less climate scenarios.
SDM tools may not work on local scale.	3	2	Focus either on collecting local data, or adapt SDM tools so local layers can be utilized.

2.2. DUC 2 on the Impact from offshore infrastructures

Figure 5. Overview of physical (blue) and virtual (green) twin components linked in DUC 2.

DUC leader(s)* and participants with organization	Asbjorn Christensen* (DTU), Patrizio Mariani (DTU), Kim Aarestrup (DTU), Lotte Pohl* (VLIZ), Jan Reubens (VLIZ), Carlota Muñiz (VLIZ), Elisabeth Debusschere (VLIZ), Jo-Hannes Nowé (VLIZ), Peter Tyack (USTAN), Jakob Tougaard (AU), Emily T Griffiths (AU)
Challenge and suggested solution	<p>The offshore industry faces challenges due to insufficient knowledge about the direct and indirect biological impacts of offshore activities on relevant and/or sensitive marine species. Current information is often incomplete and qualitative, lacking the spatial and temporal resolution required for accurate impact assessments. Additionally, current offshore industry decision-making workflows do not fully leverage biological sensor and monitoring data. This implementation gap hinders effective management and use of marine ecosystems, potentially increasing the ecological footprint of offshore infrastructure and activities.</p> <p>DUC 2 proposes to develop an interactive tool to address the challenges. The tool will integrate various types of biological sensor and monitoring data, including acoustic telemetry, biologging, and passive acoustic monitoring datasets, and consider abiotic factors like temperature and salinity. The tool's base will be species-specific habitat suitability maps, overlaying current and planned offshore infrastructures and activities.</p> <p>Additionally, a Lagrangian simulation tool that models directed movement of individuals will be incorporated, thereby enhancing the tool's representativeness of the real marine ecosystem.</p> <p>The envisioned result is a tool that enables stakeholders to plan offshore activities minimising the disturbance of marine communities by providing processed ecological data and impact assessments. This tool will support more nature-inclusive planning of offshore</p>

	infrastructure and help schedule high-impact activities during periods and in areas with lower environmental impact, promoting sustainable offshore development.
Biological monitoring and sensor resources	<p>European Tracking Network (ETN)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fish acoustic telemetry data • Fish biologging data • Harbour porpoise passive acoustic monitoring data
Data resources	<p>Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time oceanographic data layers and forecasts <p>European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data layers from various contexts (e.g. human activities, chemistry, physics, biology) <p>International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stock assessments serving as biological distribution syntheses <p>Occurrence databases such as EurOBIS (EMODnet Biology)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biological key parameters on species lifecycle, vital rates and ecosystem interactions, SDM parametrizations
Analytical resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habitat suitability mapping pipeline (Citores et al. 2020) • Seasonal density maps (Giles et al. 2016) • Connectivity analysis functionality based on Lagrangian simulation output (Christensen et al. 2018) • Relevant R packages <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ geospatial data operations (e.g. <i>terra</i>, <i>sf</i>), ○ data sourcing (e.g. <i>etn</i>, <i>eurobis</i>, <i>rgbif</i>), ○ modelling (e.g. <i>xgboost</i>, <i>mgcv</i>, <i>ranger</i>, <i>earth</i>, <i>habitat</i>, <i>R-inla</i>, <i>inlabru</i>)
Expected outputs and feedback	<p>The final product will be an interactive tool that allows stakeholders to assess potential ecosystem impacts stemming from offshore infrastructures and activities, providing an optimised knowledge base for decision-making.</p> <p>The tool will assist the determination of locations for offshore infrastructure and timing of activities to minimize disturbance to (key) communities, supporting marine spatial planning that can integrate this ecological knowledge and provide a more nature-inclusive design. In areas of insufficient data, the tool will provide estimates of uncertainty of predictions and make recommendations to reduce uncertainty for planning purposes.</p>
DTO features demonstrated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System optimisation: Empowering stakeholders and their regulators to guide decision-making to limit environmental impacts when planning offshore infrastructures and activities. • Identify data gaps & missing analytical capabilities: Transforming biological sensor and monitoring data to be usable and interpretable by stakeholders.
Stakeholders	DUC 2 focuses on stakeholders involved in the execution of environmental impact assessments, decision-making and planning of offshore infrastructures and activities. It aids sustainable marine planning by helping environmental impact assessors and offshore industry stakeholders to make more ecologically informed decisions. The tool is aligned with obligations emerging from the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008/56/EC) especially Descriptor 11 stating that the artificial introduction of offshore infrastructure in the marine environment must not adversely affect the ecosystem. It furthermore supports

	the achievement of good environmental status of European waters as per Marine Spatial Planning Directive (2014/89/EU).
Status	Ready for implementation.

Risk assessment

Risk	Likelihood (1 low, 5 high)	Severity (1 low, 5 high)	Mitigation strategy
Lacks in biological data coverage leading to limited spatio/(temporal) coverage, leading to insufficient informative power of the product.	3	4	Several local use cases with sufficient data coverage can still be developed to serve as a demonstrator case.
Stakeholders might not use the tool in the end, or not adapt planning to its suggestions.	3	4	Increase outreach activities to stakeholders. Involve stakeholders in the development of the tool, ensuring it smoothly fits into their decision-making workflows.
Key personnel leaving the DUC team.	3	2	Replace personnel.

2.3. DUC 3 on assessing pelagic biodiversity and human impact

Figure 6: Overview of physical (blue) and virtual (green) twin components linked in DUC 3.

DUC leader(s)* and participants with organization	Rune Lagaisse* (VLIZ), Felipe Artigas (CNRS ULCO), Ankita Vaswani (Hereon)
Challenge and suggested solution	Plankton, a group of aquatic plants and animals relying on currents for their passive form of movement, are used as an indicator group for tracking anthropogenic environmental disturbances brought about by the maritime industry, eutrophication, industrial wastewater, invasive species, overfishing, and climate change. In practice, the use of plankton diversity indicators is often limited by the lack of extensive observations with appropriate spatiotemporal resolution and established methods at the regional and/or subregional level. Further, mainly microscopic count data are used in calculating the common OSPAR plankton diversity indicators, but additional types of plankton data may also meet the standards for MSFD evaluation and increase the quality of scientific investigations. The combination of plankton imagery and genomic data, even though being applied for only a decade or even less (depending on the sites), is likely to complement standard routine monitoring programs such as for the assessment of Pelagic Habitats (D1) in the MSFD. To showcase the utility of plankton imagery and genomic data types, existing plankton diversity indicators, such as the common OSPAR and core HELCOM indicators, will be calculated using data products from WP3 (Task 3.1, 3.2). Similarly, other relevant data products and assessment tools, currently developed in ongoing projects (MARCO-BOLO, ANERIS, JERICO-RI, BlueCloud2026), could benefit from large-scale imagery and genomic data for a more comprehensive approach in MSFD evaluations. This demonstrator will focus on how large-scale assessments of plankton biodiversity patterns can be improved using a combination of new data types for a better evaluation of potential impacts on pelagic ecosystem functioning

	and resilience now and in the future. Furthermore, improved data streams and easy-to-use analytical tools could strengthen existing ecosystem-based approaches to management.
Biological monitoring and sensor resources	Semi-automated plankton imaging data types, mainly coming from FlowCam and ZooScan, will be used for the pelagic habitat assessments. Metabarcoding monitoring data will be used to explore genetic plankton indicators for the pelagic habitat in collaboration with the MARCO-BOLO project.
Data resources	Imaging and genetic data will either be integrated into the DTO or immediately into large scale data aggregators (EMODnet, EurOBIS) through WP3 and subsequently harvested and reformatted to meet requirements for PHI 1, 2 and 3 analytical tools under WP4.
Analytical resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plankton Lifeform Extraction Tool (PLET), (Ostle et al. 2021) • PH1 PLET tool (Holland et al. 2023) • PelHabMSFD tool (Wacquet et al. 2024)
Expected outputs and feedback	<p>Analytical outputs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PH1: plots on lifeform ratios • PH2: anomaly plots on phyto- and zooplankton biomass • PH3: plots on phyto- and zooplankton diversity <p>Products</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harvesting and preprocessing scripts from DTO/ biodiversity data aggregators • Stable and open access analytical tools for calculation of PH1, PH2 and PH3 in collaboration with OPAR WGs and original authors <p>Improved tools and the use of new data sources deliver improved plankton diversity indicators for MSFD/OSPAR. Analytical outputs will deliver knowledge of how pelagic ecosystems and associated services are impacted by human activities.</p>
DTO features demonstrated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accelerate scientific outputs integrating novel data sources from semi-automatic imaging techniques instead of traditional microscopy-based analyses • Identify data gaps & missing analytical capabilities by improving existing MSFD plankton indicator reporting
Stakeholders	Targeted end users are plankton monitoring programs, data providers and policy bodies involved in national MSFD reporting.
Status	Ready for implementation.

Risk assessment

Risk	Likelihood (1 low, 5 high)	Severity (1 low, 5 high)	Mitigation
Not getting enough time-series data for desirable reference and assessment period.	2	4	Develop ways to analytically overcome data shortage. Demonstration of the products using data from a smaller region with sufficient temporal coverage.
Tools not openly available/ no cooperation possible with authors.	4	5	Establish contact with authors and offer help in maintaining and republishing tools.

2.4. DUC 4 for spatial planning of sustainable mariculture

Figure 7. Overview of physical (blue) and virtual (green) twin components linked in DUC 4.

DUC leader(s)* and participants with organization	Gert Everaert* (VLIZ), Pascal Hablützel (VLIZ), Isabel Sousa Pinto (CIIMAR), Irene Martins (CIIMAR), Carlota Gouveia (CIIMAR), Gabriela Oliveira (CIIMAR)
Challenge and suggested solution	<p>The primary challenge in developing sustainable, circular, and zero-carbon mariculture is the limited knowledge regarding optimal geographic placement, harvest periods, and the impact of native taxa or functional groups (e.g., predators). This uncertainty can make operators hesitant to invest in low or multi-trophic aquaculture systems due to the lack of sufficient information to support the effective design, operation and production of these approaches. This demonstrator addresses this challenge by integrating <i>in situ</i> observations, monitoring data, genomic data and remote sensing data to develop both statistical and mechanistic models. The main goal of these models is to find a balanced and ecologically sustainable yield of target economic species. To achieve this, the demonstrator focusses on three axes: 1) finding suitable mariculture locations for a number of target economic species; 2) quantifying the probability of harmful effects such as biomass loss from deleterious species (e.g., grazing) on mariculture species; and 3) predicting biomass yield under various climate and management scenarios. By incorporating potential losses due to predation and providing accurate biomass estimates, these models offer enhanced decision-making insights on species selection, location, and timing for cultivation. This integrative approach aims to improve production efficiency, identify high-potential yield sites and enable more effective early warning systems for recruitment and harvesting, thereby advancing sustainable mariculture practices. The feedback loop will inform whether all relevant and proxy variables and ecosystem processes are included in the analyses. As such, future optimization of the developed models is possible.</p> <p>Traditionally, single-species habitat models are used for selecting mariculture sites. The demonstrator introduces two main innovations: incorporating potential loss of mariculture production due to predation and providing biomass estimates for mariculture products, rather than just habitat suitability. The conceptual scheme to achieve this consists of four components: stakeholder questions regarding mariculture site and timing decisions,</p>

	<p>assessment of mariculture suitability for target economic species, assessment of habitat suitability for predator species, and an integrative model that combines data to optimize decisions. This conceptual scheme will be applied in two use cases. In Belgium, the focus will be on blue mussel mariculture and predation by starfish. Blue mussel habitat suitability will be assessed using fuzzy-logic models, while starfish presence will be modelled using regression techniques like generalized additive models and validated with genetic information. Integration into an existing food web model will quantify biomass estimates for both functional groups. A similar approach will be tailored to local species and conditions in Portugal, where the target economic species is kelp, the grazing species is salema, and the integration is based on the seaweed fish interaction module based on grazing equations.</p>
<p>Biological monitoring and sensor resources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species presence-absence and abundance data (e.g. LifeWatch, OBIS, ENA, EMODnet biology). • Species biological data such as life cycle information, reproduction (e.g. FishBase, World Register of Marine Species – WoRMS). • Abiotic conditions data of the past and future scenarios under climate change. • Bathymetry data and seabed habitat information.
<p>Data resources</p>	<p>OBIS, EMODnet</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Species occurrence data <p>OBIS, EMODnet</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • eDNA for presence/absence validation of starfish in the area <p>EMBRC-ERIC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To include data needed for sampling platform, labs (EMO BON) <p>Copernicus Marine Services (CMEMS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abiotic conditions (e.g., water temperature and irradiance) <p>Bio-Oracle</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Future predictions of environmental data for climate simulations <p>EMODnet</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bathymetry, seabed habitat, physics and chemistry for abiotic conditions <p>FishBase</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fish biological data incl. life cycle and reproduction <p>SeaDataNet</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abiotic conditions (e.g., water temperature and salinity) <p>PSMSL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abiotic conditions (e.g., water temperature and bathymetry) <p>ENA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw genetic data for metabarcoding of deleterious species (to be identified)
<p>Analytical resources</p>	<p>For Belgian DUC application:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial distribution model similar to Westmeijer et al. 2019 • Foodweb model from Pint et al. 2024 <p>For Portuguese DUC application:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial distribution model similar to Westmeijer et al. (2019) with an extended Seaweed biomass model from https://github.com/CVenolia/SugarKelpDEB (Venolia et al. 2020) • Fish biomass model from https://github.com/sizespectrum/mizer (Scott, 2013)
<p>Expected outputs and feedback</p>	<p>Expected outputs from this demonstrator include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predictive models: Statistical and mechanistic models that predict biomass yield and integrate the impact of deleterious species and climate change on mariculture

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimized mariculture practices: Evidence-based recommendations on optimal species selection, geographic placement, and harvest timing to maximize yield and sustainability Validated data: Validation of model predictions using genetic information data, ensuring the reliability and accuracy of the models Early warning systems: Development of early warning systems for recruitment and harvesting, improving operational decision-making and risk management
DTO features demonstrated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enable systems research and education by integrating multiple data sources to develop advanced predictive models and validation techniques that help enhancing sustainable yields and manage risks, thereby improving decision-making in mariculture practices Identify data gaps and missing analytical capabilities through the collection of additional biotic and abiotic data to extend the application to other predator-prey interactions in other regions
Stakeholders	Mariculture innovators, marine spatial planners, research and academics.
Status	Partly ready for implementation.

Risk Assessment

Risk	Likelihood (1 low, 5 high)	Severity (1 low, 5 high)	Mitigation
Not enough baseline data from any of the mariculture sites.	3	3	Focus on regional models.
Not enough data for what-if scenario.	3	4	Generate the data within the study cases through collaboration with local stakeholders.
High rise in prices of genetic analyses or laboratory consumables which could not be foreseen.	2	3	Fall back to existing observatories nearby ACs. Reduction of samples to represent a smaller area.
Insufficient biomass data available.	3	4	Make connections with local stakeholders to provide data.

2.5. DUC 5 Ecosystem-based spatial planning and MPA management

Figure 8. Overview of physical (blue) and virtual (green) twin components linked in DUC 5.

DUC leader(s)* and participants with organization	Dan Lear* (MBA), Harvey Tyler-Walters (MBA), Heidi Tillin* (PML)
Challenge and suggested solution	<p>The Natural Capital Approach recognizes the contribution that habitats and species make to human well-being through the provision of ecosystem services that, in turn, can be converted into societal goods and benefits. Assessments of natural capital to support the sustainable management of coastal and marine resources are increasingly being implemented through Ecosystem Based Management and other policy drivers. Current assessments of ecosystem service (ES) delivery available to resource managers, policy makers and scientists are usually provided by asset-service matrices that identify the supply of ES by broad habitat type. However, while these are valuable, they do not identify the components that support the service. For example, mudflats support erosion prevention via invertebrate tubes and films of microphytobenthos and microorganisms. In addition, much sampling and monitoring data is collected at the species level and not necessarily aligned to standard habitat classifications such as the EUNIS habitat classification or the UK Marine Habitat Classification. Habitat frameworks are conceptual. Within similar habitat types there may be wide variation in the structure of the biological assemblage (species identity and abundance) that is likely to reflect ecosystem function and ultimately the provision of ecosystem services.</p> <p>The DUC will begin to fill this gap via a publicly available species traits database that will identify how benthic species support ecosystem service delivery and build asset-service matrices.</p>

	<p>Simple statistical models to enable users to identify and present ES capacity and its sensitivity to pressures from human activity will be explored to provide users with a tool to link sampled data to ES capacity.</p> <p>Biological Trait Analysis, i.e. assessment of traits (i.e., the behavioural, morphological, and reproductive characteristics) expressed by benthic species has been demonstrated to provide insight into the causes and consequences of biodiversity change that cannot be achieved using conventional taxonomic approaches. To date, trait databases have been used to consider ecological function but do not identify how species may contribute to ecosystem services and to societal good and benefits. In addition, there are identified issues around trait standardisation and terminology. We will develop a standard trait vocabulary to resolve this issue.</p> <p>This DUC aims to provide a traits database of ecosystem service delivery by benthic species and habitats. This data coupled with sensitivity to pressures data (based on species biological traits) will support assessment of the impact of human activities on supply and provision and ES. Proof of concept models have been trialled but require updating with further species information and testing to support adoption.</p> <p>The outputs will allow users to examine how management of marine resources can be improved to achieve sustainable economic and societal benefits by addressing key issues of resource use, i.e., how maritime activities affect natural capital.</p>
<p>Biological monitoring and sensor resources</p>	<p>Data we can explore using can be sourced from conventional monitoring data (trawl, grab, video survey) or derived from new monitoring eDNA, automated image analysis.</p> <p>The Trait database developed by this project (intended to be an updated version of the MarLIN (MBA) BIOTIC traits database and tool will ingest species lists. To support this, we would seek the following:</p> <p>Benthic macroinvertebrate infauna data: species identity, abundance and biomass-preferably raw and standardized for analysis: can be obtained from any source, e.g. eDNA, grab sampling, etc.</p> <p>These are prioritized for our DUC; if resources allow, we would also be interested in adding fish and other taxonomic groups (plankton, mammals) to the BIOTIC traits database.</p>
<p>Data resources</p>	<p>Biological and ecological trait information has been collected for marine species and provided by a number of on-line platforms to users from the scientific community.</p> <p>Three main types of traits are documented:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biological and ecological traits-specific characteristics of a taxon (e.g. body size or feeding type) • Taxonomic traits (e.g. paraphyletic groups) • Human-defined traits (e.g. Red List species) <p>Trait information collected by EMODnet is available through the World Register of Marine Species and the LifeWatch Species Information portal. Other trait databases that can be drawn on following trait standardisation and alignment are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FishBase: which includes a published trait database (Beuckhof et al. 2019). • Polytraits: A database on biological traits of marine polychaetes, morphological, behavioural and reproductive characteristics (Faulwetter et al. 2014).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEFAS data portal (Clare et al. 2022). Information on ten key biological traits for over a thousand marine benthic invertebrate taxa surveyed in Northwest Europe (mainly the UK shelf). • BIOTIC (MarLIN 2006) database contains information on over 40 biological trait categories. • Plymouth Marine Laboratory Trait explorer (https://www.marine-ecosystems.org.uk/).
Analytical resources	<p>The project is supported by a contractor to provide expert modelling input and development of a general user interface.</p> <p>The MarLIN website will provide the key platform for delivery, hosting the relevant supporting information (ES traits catalogue, biotope ES information) and making this publically accessible to users in the long-term to support wider use by users including the research community and managers.</p> <p>Updated biological trait information with wider application in Biological Traits Analysis will be uploaded to the MarLIN BIOTIC database (http://www.marlin.ac.uk/biotic/).</p>
Expected outputs and feedback	<p>The developed tools will support assessments based on natural capital to inform sustainable management decisions that in turn will help support the improvement and restoration of marine ecosystems. Availability and use of such tools is foundational to achieving the climate and biodiversity ambitions of national and international commitments (e.g. Paris Agreement, UN decade of Ecosystem restoration and the post-2020 global biodiversity framework).</p>
DTO features demonstrated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systems research and education based on better understanding the relations between environmental change, habitats responses, and ecosystem services leading to improved regulations and ecological sustainability • Identify gaps in data coverage and analytical capabilities the analyses will help specifying what should be measured, where, and how leading to improved monitoring programs
Stakeholders	<p>Marine spatial planners, research and academics; UK traits stakeholder group that meets every 6 months to discuss application of this project with key statutory conservation agencies and academics.</p>
Status	<p>Ready for implementation.</p>

Risk assessment

Risk	Likelihood (1 low, 5 high)	Severity (1 low, 5 high)	Mitigation
Linkages between traits, ecosystem function and services cannot be established.	1	4	Literature has identified some clear links between species, processes, functions and services. The relationship is not clear across all standard ES. The approach will explore 1-1 links between species & ES, functional groups and trait groups.
Not enough trait data already available for a sufficient database to ensure wider applicability.	3	4	Trait data is time consuming to collect. We anticipate that there will be some gaps, but we will be seeking to align terminology to identify a wide range of sources. We

			anticipate full coverage of species traits for the trial dataset.
Species observation data takes many forms, from samples based on a few species to infaunal datasets providing biomass and abundance. Creating a tool that can provide a meaningful output is a challenge.	2	3	Stakeholders and application will be considered from the outset, with an emphasis on the development of outputs. We anticipate the outputs will include user friendly plots of trait composition that can be compared over time, e.g. radar plots, pie charts, bar graph. Outputs will be shared with users for feedback as part of development.

2.6. DUC 6 on lower-trophic level biomass monitoring to inform ocean governance

Figure 9. Overview of physical (blue) and virtual (green) twin components linked in DUC 6.

DUC leader(s)* and participants with organization	Ute Brønner*, Muriel Dunn, Ralph Stevenson-Jones, Raymond Nepstad (all, Department of Climate and Environment, SINTEF Ocean), Associated partners: Neil Holdsworth (ICES), Arne Berre (SINDIG)
Challenge and suggested solution	<p>Zooplankton species like <i>Calanus</i> spp. can be abundant near the sea water surface in swarms and dense aggregations that can even be seen from space. They present a large biomass that is of interest as a food web health indicator for ocean governance and even for harvesting. However, these patches are sparse and vary with seasons and environmental conditions.</p> <p>Traditional detection methods are centred around nets and provide data consisting of single points in space and time or aggregations from net towing. As part of DTO-BioFlow, we want to develop data pipelines from alternative monitoring approaches such as sensor fusion of acoustics and optics, which can optionally be combined with adaptive data sampling including autonomous underwater robots.</p> <p>This DUC uses plankton biomass as a proxy for the abundance of higher trophic level biomass. Applying dynamic plankton biomass monitoring through combination of plankton imaging and echosounder data on stationary and mobile platforms to inform ocean governance decision making. Examples include quota management for and fishing activities that target lower trophic species, ship traffic regulations, understanding effects of climate change and water quality on plankton biomass and thus ecosystem.</p> <p>The proposed DUC will leverage autonomous detection of zooplankton swarms using acoustics (specifically echosounders) and characterization of the species within the swarms using optics (specifically SINTEF Silhouette camera <i>SilCam</i>).</p>

	The solution will be tested in SINTEF’s OceanLab observatory in the Trondheim fjord, Norway and it will be based on a DTO for water quality and particles developed in the Iliad project.
Biological monitoring and sensor resources	<p>Active acoustics by echosounder</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sound scattering layers <p>Optics by SilCam</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Particle size distributions • Particle classification (PyOPIA pipeline with neural network) <p>Systematic and opportunistic observation networks</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OceanLab observatory • Combining monitoring efforts with projects of opportunity (Iliad, SFI Harvest, DiverSea, AMBIOS, HYPISO, and more)
Data resources	<p>Norkyst800 ocean model data (https://thredds.met.no/)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EOV <p>Ocean observations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EOV, river outlet (fresh water, sediment) <p>Satellite images</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ocean colour <p>Socio-economic data (https://www.barentswatch.no/)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine traffic, locations, and turnover in European ports and marinas
Analytical resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OpenDrift (https://opendrift.github.io/) transport modelling for trajectory predictions
Expected outputs and feedback	<p>Surface sensor platforms (acoustics) will inform and trigger subsurface sensor platforms through the DTO where to sample biomass using optical sensors.</p> <p>The results will be shown on a map and a dashboard and shared to the public DTO infrastructure for long-term assessment and monitoring (e.g. algae blooms and their change over time and in relation to climate).</p>
DT features demonstrated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense, anticipate, and react to significant events through plankton biomass detection • Identify gaps in data coverage and analytical capabilities leading to improved monitoring programs
Stakeholders	<p>Target end users include environmental agencies (ocean governance), municipalities (ocean health & water quality), port administrations (marine traffic), and research institutes. We are currently in active collaboration with the Trondheim port authority, the Trøndelag county on fjord health monitoring and governance and researchers at SINTEF Ocean and the Norwegian university for science and technology on monitoring and modelling of plankton ecosystems.</p> <p>More specifically, the DUC is based on active collaboration with the Norwegian University of Science and Technology on plankton ecology underwater robotics on OceanLab and FjordLab infrastructure, www.oceanlab.no.</p> <p>More specifically, the DUC is based on active collaboration with the Norwegian University of Science and Technology on plankton ecology underwater robotics on OceanLab and FjordLab infrastructure, www.oceanlab.no.</p>
Status	Ready for implementation.

Risk assessment

Risk	Likelihood (1 low, 5 high)	Severity (1 low, 5 high)	Mitigation strategy
Gaps in biological data coverage leading to limited temporal coverage, leading to insufficient informative power of the product.	3	4	Extend the sampling window and automate as many triggers as possible to collect enough data for the demonstrator case.
Stakeholders might not use the tool in the end, or not adapt planning to its suggestions.	3	4	Increase outreach activities to stakeholders. Involve stakeholders in the development of the tool, ensuring it smoothly fits into their decision-making workflows.
Key personnel leaving the DUC team.	3	2	Replace personnel.

2.7. DUC 7 on ecosystem services, including carbon sequestration

Figure 10. Overview of physical (blue) and virtual (green) twin components linked in DUC 7.

DUC leader(s)* and participants with organization	Lionel Guidi* (CNRS), Hervé Claustre* (CNRS), Madeleine Walker (CNRS)
Challenge and suggested solution	<p>Quantifying the amount of carbon dioxide (CO₂) stored in the ocean over climatically significant timescales is hindered by the lack of comprehensive and integrated global carbon transport observations. Large uncertainties associated with ocean carbon flux arise from critical observational gaps and insufficiently parameterized key processes (e.g., particle fragmentation) in models. A global 3D/4D product of particle size distribution and carbon flux is essential to study the role of particle dynamics in carbon export and to support modelling activities (initialization, parameterization, validation) related to carbon sequestration. This DUC aims to provide a global carbon flux (carbon export) product based on measurements of particle size and concentration from an in-situ quantitative imagery instrument, the Underwater Vision Profiler (UVP), deployed on various platforms (rosettes, gliders, BGC-Argo floats, moorings, etc.). The UVP provides measurements of particles > 100 μm and zooplankton (Picheral et al. 2010) that allow deriving particle size distributions (PSDs) and concentrations. Particle data available from UVPs is increasing exponentially and filling spatial and temporal observational gaps, as UVPs can be deployed on autonomous platforms in regions and time periods not easily accessible to other observation platforms such as ships or satellites (Claustre et al. 2021). Using UVP observations in concert with other carbon flux measurements will enable better estimations of global carbon flux and sequestration.</p> <p>The use case will be built on the following activities:</p> <p>First, the construction of a global database of carbon flux measurements, gathering data from (1) drifting and moored sediment traps, using literature reviews and available data in</p>

	<p>different repositories (e.g. Pangaea, SeaNoe, etc.); (2) Thorium/Uranium deficit measurements, assembled and converted into carbon fluxes; (3) all other available carbon flux measurements obtainable through database queries and literature reviews. These independent flux measurements will be used as “truth” or “benchmarking” measurements to validate the global carbon flux/export estimates derived from the particle size and concentration measurements and will be managed outside of EDITO.</p> <p>Second, UVP PSDs and concentrations collected from ship-based rosette deployments, BGC-Argo profiles, gliders, moorings, and other platforms, will be compiled to obtain a global dataset of PSDs and concentrations. A general model of PSDs (Junge-type, quadratic, exponential decrease, etc.) will be inferred from this global dataset.</p> <p>Third, environmental data associated with surface (0-200m) PSDs and concentrations will be gathered to upscale the PSD model parameters derived from the activities above, using machine learning.</p> <p>Fourth, a relationship between the parameters of the global PSD and particle flux data gathered during the first step of the analysis will be derived to convert PSD and concentration at global scale to carbon flux and export.</p> <p>This product, developed in the four steps described above, will be made available at weekly and at least 1° resolution. The model will be updated annually based on (1) a fast-growing UVP PSD and concentration database; (2) regular updates of the carbon flux benchmarking database; (3) updates of the algorithm linking PSD and remote sensing data.</p> <p>This DUC will allow us to monitor carbon flux and export changes over time in a changing climate, and to assess the ocean’s role in sequestering carbon, with known changes in phytoplankton distribution and concentration affected by changes in ocean temperature, salinity and stratification. In the longer term, this product could become essential to support ocean (and deep-sea) governance, particularly if it is provided in near-real time. Indeed, in the context of the eventual implementation of marine carbon dioxide removal (mCDR) approaches promoted by the blue economy, observation systems will need to be implemented to provide the data and products required for monitoring, verification and efficiency reporting for carbon capture and sequestration.</p>
<p>Biological monitoring and sensor resources</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UVP observations (EcoPart), including from UVPs deployed on BGC-Argo floats • Global marine environmental observations • Other global carbon flux measurements (sediment traps, Th/U measurements)
<p>Data resources</p>	<p>UVP PSDs and concentrations under CC BY licenses will be available in the EcoPart application, and eventually in the EU DTO.</p> <p>The model will also make use of various environmental data from World Ocean Atlas, Copernicus Marine Service, IFREMER, and GEMCO.</p> <p>Benchmarking carbon flux measurements from sediment traps, Th/U deficit measurements, and other sources will be obtained via database queries and literature reviews and maintained in a separate database.</p> <p>The main infrastructures contributing to this DUC are EcoPart, which holds all particle size measurements from all UVPs, and the Coriolis Global Data Assembly Center, which is one of the two mirror sites delivering OneArgo global data, including UVP data acquired by BGC-</p>

	Argo floats. The real-time quality control of UVP data will be made identical between EcoPart and the Coriolis GDAC; some actions related to this quality control are planned as part of projects BlueANERIS (2023-2026) and Euro-Argo-ONE (led by the Euro-Argo ERIC, 2025-2028).
Analytical resources	Machine learning algorithm (XGBOOST) to convert PSD and concentration at global scale to carbon flux and export. This code is currently developed as part of this DUC.
Expected outputs and feedback	Analyses will produce maps showing global carbon flux and export, enabling the evaluation of carbon flux and export changes over time. The impact of phytoplankton distribution and concentration changes on carbon sequestration will also be investigated, as well as other changes in the ocean (temperature, salinity, stratification). Results are expected to lead to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expanded spatial and temporal carbon flux observations Improved carbon flux estimates in models Better integration of observation systems to improve carbon sequestration models and to evaluate marine carbon dioxide removal (mCDR) approaches
DTO features demonstrated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accelerate research outputs by consolidating existing measurements, and exploiting autonomous sensors (UVPs) to add additional carbon flux measurements to models Identify gaps in data coverage and analytical capabilities by filling the data gaps through an expansion of UVP observations
Stakeholders	Target end users include members of the biogeochemical oceanography community working on carbon flux, ocean and deep-sea governance stakeholders, and stakeholders in marine carbon dioxide removal (mCDR) approaches.
Status	Ready for implementation.

Risk assessment

Risk	Likelihood (1 low, 5 high)	Severity (1 low, 5 high)	Mitigation strategy
Uncertainties associated with carbon flux measurements from various data sources in the literature difficult to reconcile.	4	2	We can still run the model, but uncertainties may be large.
Inability to establish a relationship linking PSD and concentration to carbon flux.	2	5	Investigate other analytical tools.
Insufficient UVP data with CC-BY licenses in EcoPart.	1	2	Encourage UVP data providers to use CC-BY licenses; possibly partially automate the creation of EcoPart accounts and projects for principal investigators deploying UVPs on Argo floats to ensure that data enters EcoPart. Sufficient UVP CC-BY data already exists in EcoPart for a first iteration of the proposed model.

2.8. DUC 8 on Machine Learning for ocean colour seasonal forecasting (chlorophyll-a and primary production)

Figure 11. Overview of physical (blue) and virtual (green) twin components linked in DUC 8.

DUC leader(s)* and participants with organization	Gabriela Martinez Balbontin* (MOi), Stefano Ciavatta* (MOi)
Challenge and suggested solution	Accurate ocean colour (chlorophyll, primary production) trends are crucial for our understanding of oceanic ecosystems, carbon cycles, and fisheries management. Machine learning algorithms can significantly enhance the accuracy of existing datasets and help with future predictions by leveraging the vast amounts of available data. Positive preliminary results have been obtained by applying convolutional neural networks to physical ocean forecasts to generate seasonal chlorophyll-a predictions. These can be further expanded to other variables of interest, such as primary production, and further refined to increase regional accuracy.
Biological monitoring and sensor resources	Remote sensing data from Copernicus Marine Services (mostly GlobColour at this point)
Data resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ocean colour remote sensing data from Copernicus Marine Services (GlobColour) Physical ocean data from GLORYS12 (ocean reanalysis from Mercator Ocean used for training the neural network) and SEAS5 (multi-member forecasts generated by the ECMWF to generate the biogeochemical prediction)
Analytical resources	Machine learning algorithms (different approaches to be tested & selected based on the available data).

Expected outputs and feedback	Seasonal chlorophyll and primary production forecasts generated by machine learning algorithms based on physical ocean forecasts.
DTO features demonstrated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sense and anticipate significant events by improved monitoring and understanding of ecosystem responses to climate variability. This could help with management strategies based on forecasted data (applications in fisheries, aquaculture, algal blooms, ecosystem surveillance, etc.) • Accelerate research outputs by enabling “What-if” scenarios to different physical ocean states
Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copernicus Marine Services • Local and regional administrations and decision-makers (E.g. Mercator Ocean). • Specific actors and stakeholders will be defined as the project progresses and results are obtained, since this DUC was initiated later than the others and still in the research phase.
Status	Ready for implementation.

Risk assessment

Risk	Likelihood (1 low, 5 high)	Severity (1 low, 5 high)	Mitigation strategy
Insufficient data.	4	2	Adapt algorithms to make the most out of available data and look for additional sources.
Uncertainties and biases associated with the data.	4	2	Compare obtained forecasts to additional independent datasets.
Poor explainability of obtained predictions.	3	2	Use surrogate models and interpretability techniques to understand what is causing any given prediction.

3. Conclusions

- Eight scientific investigations have been designed as DUCs to guide the implementation of biological data and analysis resources into the EU Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO). These outlines will lead the implementation phase of the DUCs.
- The most common Digital Twin (DT) feature and added value that DTO Bioflow DUCs will provide is the identification of data gaps and missing analytical capabilities (7 DUCs), followed by the sense and anticipation of significant events (3 DUCs), together with the acceleration of scientific outputs (3 DUCs). Systems research and education will be provided by 2 DUCs, while system optimization and engineering will be delivered by one of them.
- The potential risks with major severity identified by DUCs are “Tools not openly available/ no cooperation possible with authors” (DUC 3) and the “Inability to establish a relationship linking PSD and concentration to carbon flux” (DUC 7).

4. References

- Beukhof, E., Dencker, T. S., Palomares, M. L., & Maureaud, A. (2019). A trait collection of marine fish species from North Atlantic and Northeast Pacific continental shelf seas. *Pangaea*, 1, 12.
- Björnsson, B., Borrebaeck, C., Elander, N., Gasslander, T., Gawel, D. R., Gustafsson, M., ... & Swedish Digital Twin Consortium. (2020). Digital twins to personalize medicine. *Genome medicine*, 12, 1-4.
- Budaev, S., Dumitru, M. L., Enberg, K., Handeland, S. O., Higginson, A. D., Kristiansen, T. S., ... & Giske, J. (2024). Premises for a digital twin of the Atlantic salmon in its world: Agency, robustness, subjectivity and prediction. *Aquaculture, Fish and Fisheries*, 4(1), e153.
- Calewaert, J. B., Sierra-Correa, P. C., McMeel, O., Busumprah, P. T., Crosman, K., de Boer, G., ... & Zinkann, A. C. (2024). *Ocean Decade Vision 2030 White Papers—Challenge 8: Create a digital representation of the ocean.*
- Chamberlain, S., Oldoni, D., & Waller, J. (2022). *rgbif: interface to the global biodiversity information facility API.*
- Christensen, A., Mariani, P., & Payne, M. R. (2018). A generic framework for individual-based modelling and physical-biological interaction. *Plos One*, 13(1), e0189956.
- Citores, L., Ibaibarriaga, L., Lee, D. J., Brewer, M. J., Santos, M., & Chust, G. (2020). Modelling species presence–absence in the ecological niche theory framework using shape-constrained generalized additive models. *Ecological Modelling*, 418, 108926.
- Clare, D. S., Bolam, S. G., McIlwaine, P. S., Garcia, C., Murray, J. M., & Eggleton, J. D. (2022). Biological traits of marine benthic invertebrates in Northwest Europe. *Scientific Data*, 9(1), 339.
- Claustre, H., Legendre, L., Boyd, P. W., & Levy, M. (2021). The oceans' biological carbon pumps: Framework for a research observational community approach. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 780052.
- de Koning, K., Broekhuijsen, J., Kühn, I., Ovaskainen, O., Taubert, F., Endresen, D., ... & Grimm, V. (2023). Digital twins: dynamic model-data fusion for ecology. *Trends in ecology & evolution*, 38(10), 916-926.
- Dietze, M. C., Fox, A., Beck-Johnson, L. M., Betancourt, J. L., Hooten, M. B., Jarnevich, C. S., ... & White, E. P. (2018). Iterative near-term ecological forecasting: Needs, opportunities, and challenges. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(7), 1424-1432.
- Evans, M. R., Grimm, V., Johst, K., Knuuttila, T., De Langhe, R., Lessells, C. M., ... & Benton, T. G. (2013). Do simple models lead to generality in ecology?. *Trends in ecology & evolution*, 28(10), 578-583.
- Faulwetter, M. S., Markantonatou, M. V., Pavloudi, M. C., Papageorgiou, N., Keklikoglou, M. K., Chatzinikolaou, E., ... & Arvanitidis, C. (2014). Polytraits: A database on biological traits of marine polychaetes. *Biodiversity data journal*, (2).
- Føre, M., Alver, M. O., Alfredsen, J. A., Rasheed, A., Hukkelås, T., Bjelland, H. V., ... & Papandroulakis, N. (2024). Digital Twins in intensive aquaculture—Challenges, opportunities and future prospects. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 218, 108676.
- Fuller, A., Fan, Z., Day, C., & Barlow, C. (2020). Digital twin: Enabling technologies, challenges and open research. *IEEE access*, 8, 108952-108971.
- Gilles, A., Viquerat, S., Becker, E. A., Forney, K. A., Geelhoed, S. C. V., Haelters, J., ... & Aarts, G. (2016). Seasonal habitat-based density models for a marine top predator, the harbor porpoise, in a dynamic environment. *Ecosphere*, 7(6), e01367.

Grieves, M., & Vickers, J. (2017). Digital twin: Mitigating unpredictable, undesirable emergent behavior in complex systems. *Transdisciplinary perspectives on complex systems: New findings and approaches*, 85-113.

Grieves, M. (2014). Digital twin: manufacturing excellence through virtual factory replication. *White paper*, 1(2014), 1-7.

Hartog, J. R., Spillman, C. M., Smith, G., & Hobday, A. J. (2023). Forecasts of marine heatwaves for marine industries: Reducing risk, building resilience and enhancing management responses. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography*, 209, 105276.

Hassani, H., Huang, X., & MacFeely, S. (2022). Enabling digital twins to support the UN SDGs. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, 6(4), 115.

Holland, M. (2023). PH1_PLET_tool. Available via: https://github.com/hollam2/PH1_PLET_tool

Jones, D., Snider, C., Nassehi, A., Yon, J., & Hicks, B. (2020). Characterising the Digital Twin: A systematic literature review. *CIRP journal of manufacturing science and technology*, 29, 36-52.

Kraus, R. (2023). Ballast Water Management in Ports: Monitoring, Early Warning and Response Measures to Prevent Biodiversity Loss and Risks to Human Health. *Journal of marine science and engineering*, 11(11), 2144.

Laubenbacher, R., Sluka, J. P., & Glazier, J. A. (2021). Using digital twins in viral infection. *Science*, 371(6534), 1105-1106.

Li, X., Lee, E. J., Lilja, S., Loscalzo, J., Schäfer, S., Smelik, M., ... & Benson, M. (2022). A dynamic single cell-based framework for digital twins to prioritize disease genes and drug targets. *Genome medicine*, 14(1), 48.

Marshall, C., Tyler-Walters, H., Langmead, O., Jackson, E., Lear, D., & Somerfield, P. (2006). BIOTIC—biological traits information catalogue. *Marine life information network*.

Massicotte, P., & South, A. (2024). rnatuarearth: world map data from natural earth. *R package version 1.0*. 1.9000.

McMurdie, P. J., & Holmes, S. (2013). phyloseq: an R package for reproducible interactive analysis and graphics of microbiome census data. *PloS one*, 8(4), e61217.

Nativi, S., Mazzetti, P., & Craglia, M. (2021). Digital ecosystems for developing digital twins of the earth: The destination earth case. *Remote Sensing*, 13(11), 2119.

Ostle, C., Paxman, K., Graves, C. A., Arnold, M., Artigas, F., Atkinson, A., ... & McQuattors-Gollop, A. (2021). The Plankton Lifeform Extraction Tool: a digital tool to increase the discoverability and usability of plankton time-series data. *Earth System Science Data Discussions*, 2021, 1-73.

Perez, H. D., Wassick, J. M., & Grossmann, I. E. (2022). A digital twin framework for online optimization of supply chain business processes. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 166, 107972.

Picheral, M., Guidi, L., Stemmann, L., Karl, D. M., Iddaoud, G., & Gorsky, G. (2010). The Underwater Vision Profiler 5: An advanced instrument for high spatial resolution studies of particle size spectra and zooplankton. *Limnology and Oceanography: Methods*, 8(9), 462-473.

Pint, S., Stevens, M., Musimwa, R., Standaert, W., De Troch, M., van Oevelen, D., ... & Everaert, G. (2024). A food web model of the Southern Bight of the North Sea. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 255, 107256.

Rasheed, A., San, O., & Kvamsdal, T. (2020). Digital twin: Values, challenges and enablers from a modeling perspective. *IEEE access*, 8, 21980-22012.

Scott, F., Blanchard, J.L., & Andersen, K.H. (2013). mizer: Multi-speciessIZE spectrum modelling in R. *R package version 0.1*. Available via: <https://github.com/sizespectrum/mizer>

Stumpf, R. P., Tomlinson, M. C., Calkins, J. A., Kirkpatrick, B., Fisher, K., Nierenberg, K., ... & Wynne, T. T. (2009). Skill assessment for an operational algal bloom forecast system. *Journal of Marine Systems*, 76(1-2), 151-161.

Tessarolo, G., Ladle, R. J., Lobo, J. M., Rangel, T. F., & Hortal, J. (2021). Using maps of biogeographical ignorance to reveal the uncertainty in distributional data hidden in species distribution models. *Ecography*, 44(12), 1743-1755.

The European Green Deal. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions (COM(2019) 640 Final). (2019). Available online: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52019DC0640> (accessed on 16 February 2023).

Venolia, C. T., Lavaud, R., Green-Gavrielidis, L. A., Thornber, C., & Humphries, A. T. (2020). Modeling the growth of sugar kelp (*Saccharina latissima*) in aquaculture systems using dynamic energy budget theory. *Ecological Modelling*, 430, 109151.

Wacquet, G., Aubert, A., Budria, A., Duflos, M., Mialet, B., Rombouts, I., & Artigas, L. F. (2024). PelHabMSFD. Available via: <https://github.com/IFREMER-LERBL/PelHabMSFD>

Westmeijer, G., Everaert, G., Pirlet, H., De Clerck, O., & Vandegehuchte, M. B. (2019). Mechanistic niche modelling to identify favorable growth sites of temperate macroalgae. *Algal Research*, 41, 101529.

